

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS FOR TEACHING PRESCHOOLERS 5-7 YEARS OLD VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN RUSSIAN

Nigina Rakhmatova

Senior Lecturer branch of the Herzen State Pedagogical University in Tashkent

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***Abstract.** This article explores the role of methodological recommendations in the study of Russian as a second language in preschool institutions. The article discusses some methodological techniques and means of improving the content and quality of teaching Russian as a non-native language at any stage of personality development, and in this case, preschool age. A new method of correct speech development is proposed as a necessary condition for the formation of a child's personality.*

***Keywords:** speech development, bilingual children, correct communication, preschool institution, language environment, vocabulary.*

INTRODUCTION. Speech is a social phenomenon and serves as a means of communication between people. Timely correct speech development is a necessary condition for the formation of a child's personality. It is always interesting and pleasant to communicate with a person who has the skills of beautiful, correct, noticeable simple speech. And therefore speech should be developed from childhood.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan there is a very great need to study the great Russian language. In Tashkent alone there are more than 334 state kindergartens [1] and more than 180 private kindergartens with Russian as the language of instruction [2]. And these are not the last indicators - the number of such kindergartens is growing. These figures indicate an increased need for learning the Russian language.

Children are taught Russian in multinational preschool organizations in the absence of a Russian language environment, and a significant proportion of children do not speak Russian. Due to their age, they are not able to independently comprehend the meaning of the Russian language and realize the need to study it. Therefore, from the very first moments of organized teaching of the Russian language, children are explained in their native language why the Russian language is needed in life, that they will soon go to school where they will study Russian, and in order to study well, already in kindergarten they should learn to speak Russian.

Russian Preschool children studying Russian in multinational preschool organizations master it in an artificially created language environment, which should be developmental in nature.

The concept of a language development environment includes both the language environment itself and the child's subject-development environment.

Children with different levels of Russian language proficiency can enter multinational preschool institutions - from complete ignorance to proficiency at the level of a peer native speaker of Russian.

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN RUSSIAN AS A NATIVE LANGUAGE. The methodology for teaching Russian to preschool children suggests

conducting a linguistic examination of children to determine their level of Russian language proficiency in accordance with the following parameters:

- 1) the child does not speak Russian at all (recently resettled from a rural area);
- 2) the child does not speak Russian as a means of communication (knows several dozen Russian words);
- 3) the child knows, understands and uses frequent words, phrases, etiquette forms in speech, understands the address of an adult; can recite a short poem;
- 4) the child understands simple texts, is able to describe game actions, and use simple syntactic structures; engage in simple dialogue in certain communication situations;
- 5) the child understands spoken speech, knows Russian fairy tales, songs, proverbs, sayings, and can communicate with familiar Russian speakers;
- 6) the child independently uses the language in various life communication situations, understands spontaneous speech, and is able to participate in conversation at the level of a native speaker of his age.

Therefore, when teaching the Russian language in preschool organizations, it is necessary to implement a differentiated and individual approach [3].

When selecting the content of teaching the Russian language to preschoolers and primary schoolchildren (bilingual children with Russian as a second language), it is necessary:

- correlation with the age of children learning Russian as a new language and the characteristics of their development;
- organizing classes in such a way as to immerse the child in speech (immersion technique);
- highlighting as one of the main parameters of mastering a new language the volume and composition of active and passive vocabulary, control over its use;
- use of ways to develop vocabulary that are appropriate to age and level of proficiency in a new language: including words and expressions in context, training them in various entertaining exercises, accompanying words with videos (pictures, realities, gestures, facial expressions, movements), memorizing words in connection with their equivalents in the native language, studying word formation, word composition, word compatibility in a playful way.

When entering a preschool educational organization, the starting level of language proficiency is different for all students. It is necessary to conduct entrance testing to determine individual routes (correction program for children experiencing difficulties in mastering the Russian language). The standard offers two types of meters: methods for measuring the level of proficiency in types of speech activities - listening, speaking, reading and writing; testing, which determines the level of knowledge [4].

RESEARCH METHOD. The development of coherent oral speech is the main task in the process of teaching language to preschoolers. To master the skills of dialogical speech, you should reinforce memorized words, standard sentences, and grammatical forms in question-and-answer exercises. Children must learn not only to answer questions, but also to ask them. Therefore, it is important that at each lesson exercises are carried out in the form of both answering questions and asking questions. These exercises are performed with the demonstration of subject and plot pictures, objects, actions, and models. At each lesson, the child must master speech actions in the scope of one dialogic unity, built on the studied lexical and grammatical material, which is important for participation in educational communication. When performing these exercises, along with mastering words, children are taught the ability to use the narrative and interrogative

intonation of a Russian sentence. The teacher gives a sample question, and then the children themselves ask it.

CONCLUSION. So, to conduct effective teaching classes in the Russian language it is necessary: 1) to determine the topics of communicative and speech situations within the framework of organized activities of children; 2) select language and speech didactic material that corresponds to the age characteristics of bilingual children, the principles, goals and objectives of teaching Russian as a second language; 3) select adapted texts for listening and speaking; 4) create speech models and standard sentences; 5) select means, forms and methods of teaching the Russian language [5].

In general, teaching the Russian (non-native) language to bilingual children, taking into account the sociolinguistic and methodological conditions for the formation of early bilingualism, is important in the pedagogical process of a preschool educational organization and actively contributes to solving the problems of moral, physical, artistic and aesthetic development of children.

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